

Self-affirmative Discourse on Broadcast Media Programmes and Insecurity Management in Pluralistic Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was carried out to examine the role of broadcast media in managing insecurity in Nigeria. Anchored on the social responsibility media theory and supported by the agenda setting theory, the research adopted a library research method and synthesis discourse analysis. The findings revealed that broadcast media programmes have a tremendous impact on insecurity management by raising public awareness, disseminating critical information and fostering a culture of vigilance. However, the media sometimes frame security issues in a way that promotes regional and ethnic sentiments rather than addressing the root causes of insecurity. The study also identified several challenges facing the broadcast media, including limited access, ownership influence, poor funding, and misinformation. It was concluded that despite these challenges, the broadcast media have a positive contribution to make in managing insecurity when used effectively. The study recommended that broadcast media should prioritise balanced reporting, avoid sensationalism and promote national unity. Regular training and capacity-building programmes for media professionals are also essential to enhance their skills in reporting security issues and countering misinformation.

Keywords: Broadcast Media Programmes, Security and Insecurity, Insecurity Management, Pluralistic Nigeria

Introduction

Globally, the mass media play a crucial role in disseminating information that influences public opinion and promotes societal values aimed at addressing pressing issues. One of the most critical challenges facing societies today is insecurity, prompting scholars to assess the role of the media in mitigating this problem (Bappayo, 2023; Edatejirhaye, Ogunwuyi & Olawunmi, 2022; Ehigiator, Asemah, & Nwaoboli, 2023; Ottah & Okpoko, 2024). Like many other nations, Nigeria continues to grapple with escalating security threats, despite possessing abundant natural and human resources. The prevalence of

insecurity manifested in banditry, *Boko Haram* insurgency, farmer-herder clashes, kidnappings for ransom, ritual killings, armed robbery, assassinations, ethnic agitations, and cult-related violence has become one of the greatest threats to national stability in the 21st century (Odishika, 2021).

As highlighted by Nwokoro, Akpan & Peter (2023, p. 150), “the volatile security situation in Nigeria, particularly with the emergence of *Boko Haram*, has drawn national attention. Reports of kidnappings, herdsman attacks, destruction of properties, and other violent acts now dominate the daily news cycle.” According to the 2024 Nigeria Humanitarian Response Plan, approximately 7.9 million people are projected to require humanitarian aid. This includes 2.1 million internally displaced persons, 1.9 million returnees facing inadequate access to essential services, and 3.9 million host community members (UNHCR, 2025).

Similarly, the rise in terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, herder-farmer conflicts and related crimes has escalated to the extent that Nigeria ranked 143rd out of 163 nations on the Global Peace Index in 2022 (Atai & Esetang, 2024; Ehigiator, Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2023; Musa, Che, Isma & Siti, 2024; Nasiru, 2020; Onwe et al., 2024). Notable incidents highlighting Nigeria's security crisis include the 2014 Chibok girls' abduction, the 2018 Dapchi school kidnappings, the 2011 bombing of the United Nations building in Abuja, the 2021 invasion of the Nigerian Defence Academy, and the 2022 Abuja-Kaduna train attack (Onwe *et al* 2024). Unemployment, poverty, corruption, poor governance, weak security structures, ethnic and religious divisions, and marginalisation are some of the factors contributing to Nigeria's worsening insecurity (Atai & Esetang, 2024; Nasiru, 2020).

The consequences of the security challenges in Nigeria have been severe, resulting in school closures, a decline in food production, reduced investments, targeted attacks on security personnel, destruction of public infrastructure, and increased ransom-driven kidnappings (Abdullah, 2022; Onwe et al., 2024; Ugwu, 2022); significantly hampering socio-economic growth, despite the country's vast resources (Soho, 2024), making it imperative for all stakeholders, including the broadcast media, to contribute towards finding lasting solutions (Dare, Bamidele & Oluwasanmi, 2020; Elliot, Ifeoma & Etumnu, 2024; Ottah & Okpoko, 2024; Santas, 2015; Musa, Che, Isma & Siti, 2024; Santas & Alu, 2018).

Consequently, prior studies and sources have affirmed to the fact that the media, particularly the broadcast have different role to play in the management of insecurity (Abdullahi & Dango, 2023; Achakpaikyo et al., 2022; Bappayo, 2023; Santas & Kente, 2020; Dare, Bamidele & Oluwasanmi, 2020; Edefejirhaye, Ogunwuyi & Olawunmi, 2022; Elliot, Ifeoma & Etumnu, 2024; Iheanacho, Jumbo & Etumnu, 2021; Kiche & Simiyu, 2022; Ottah & Okpoko, 2024; Santas, Inobemhe & Isah, 2022). According to Abdullahi & Dango (2023) the broadcast media play a vital role in peacebuilding and national development, possessing the ability to inform, educate, and mobilise the public on security matters. Ottah & Okpoko (2024, p. 2) note that the “mass media serve as

effective tools for promoting national security when policymakers harness them strategically to advance peace initiatives.” Research by Bappayo (2023) highlighted that broadcast media contribute to reducing insecurity by advocating national interests, disseminating security updates, and evaluating government efforts in crime prevention.

Also, there are dedicated specialised programmes to security management on Nigerian broadcast stations in Nigeria. Examples include Security Watch (Nigeria Info FM), Crime Alert (RayPower FM), Security Alert (Channels TV) and The Security Report (Arise News), among others (Elliot, Ifeoma & Etumnu, 2024). However, the dearth of a specific study focusing on “Self-Affirmative Discourse on Broadcast Media Programmes and Insecurity Management in Pluralistic Nigeria” is why this study is imperative.

Conceptual Clarification of Broadcast Media Programmes

Broadcast media programme encompasses the various types of audio and video materials, including news, entertainment, educational programmes and commercials, that are distributed to a wide audience through radio, television, or other electronic media of communication (Hao, 2024). A broadcast media programme can take the form of information, education and entertainment created to meet certain specific needs of the viewing or listening audience. It can be classified into two broad categories; spoken word and music. Spoken word according to Duyile (2005) in Esiri & Onwubere (n.d), are talks, discussions, educational broadcasting, interviews, drama, documentary, magazines, news and current affairs programmes and religious broadcasting; while music programmes include pre-recorded programme, live musical performance of all kinds and variety of entertainment. On the other hand, James & Ward (1998), cited in Esiri & Onwubere (n.d), classified broadcast programme into four major categories, namely:

- a. Public affairs or programmes which are made up of news, interview, sports, documentary among others.
- b. Entertainment programmes which are drama, musicals and talk shows.
- c. Children’s programmes which are moonlight tales, drama, educational programmes and cartoons.
- d. Enlightenment programmes, mostly sponsored by government and its agencies.

In Nigeria, radio and television programming content is shaped by a mix of local and foreign programming, with a regulatory push towards prioritising local content and cultural identity. The NBC enforces a policy requiring a significant portion of programming to be locally produced, aiming to promote Nigerian culture and identity. Nigerian radio and television stations feature a wide range of programming, including news, current affairs, entertainment, music, drama, and educational programmes (NBC, 2016).

Security and Insecurity

Security is a multifaceted concept that has evolved over time, depending on the historical and societal context (Rothschild, 1995). In its simplest form, security refers to safety, protection from harm, and freedom from risk. As emphasised by Zabadi (2011), protection is fundamental to human existence—without it, other aspects of life become meaningless (Nasiru, 2020). Imobighe (2001) also argues that security is essential for individuals to engage in productive activities and for states to foster human development and societal well-being. William (2008) defines security as a means of mitigating threats to cherished values, particularly when unchecked threats could endanger the existence of individuals or communities. Security is described as a system of safeguarding people, information, and property from harmful influences and threats. It implies a condition where individuals can live freely within a given space without fear of real or perceived danger (Nasiru, 2020).

Conversely, insecurity is the opposite of security and is a growing global concern. It is commonly associated with uncertainty, instability, and a lack of safety. Insecurity has been defined as exposure to risks such as poverty, illness, violence, and oppression (Bustillo & Velloso, 2016). Odey (2019) describes insecurity as a state of vulnerability, fear, and anxiety resulting from perceived or real threats. Insecurity can lead to fear, psychological distress, and a decline in overall well-being. Ajodo-Adebanjoko & Ugwuoke (2014) define insecurity as a state where individuals or communities experience threats such as violence, harassment, and social unrest. The United Nations Development Programme, Human Development Report (1994) describes human security as protection from both immediate and structural threats, including hunger, disease, and economic instability.

Some scholars emphasise the effects of insecurity on individuals and communities, while others focus on its broader implications for economic and political stability (Musa, Che, Isma & Siti, 2024). Economic inequality and global disparities further exacerbate insecurity, as wealthier nations are often better equipped to address security threats than developing countries (Wijkman & Timberlake, 2021).

In Nigeria, insecurity manifests in multiple forms, including terrorism, armed banditry, kidnapping, and intercommunal conflicts. These security challenges have prompted increased global and national focus on addressing security threats. However, corruption and mismanagement of security funds have often hindered effective responses in many developing countries, including Nigeria (Wijkman & Timberlake, 2021). Beland (2005) defines insecurity as “*a state of fear or anxiety resulting from a real or perceived lack of protection*” (p. 89). William (2008) argues that security is inherently linked to political and social stability—without security, political institutions become unstable and economic development is hindered.

Insecurity Management

The concept of insecurity management is so prominent and requires further interrogation due to the level of insecurity in many parts of the world. In Nigeria, the high rate of

insecurity perpetuated by different forms and groups of criminals significantly affects the national peace, unity and development of the country in different areas (Magaji, Kari, Otakey & Jafaru, 2024). To manage as clearly defined by Fayol (1916) in Kaehler & Grundei (2019) “is to forecast and plan, to organise, to command, to co-ordinate and to control. To foresee and provide means examining the future and drawing up the plan of action. To organise means building up the dual structure, material and human, of the undertaking. To command means maintaining activity among the personnel. To co-ordinate means binding together, unifying and harmonising all activity and effort. To control means seeing that everything occurs in conformity with established rule and expressed command” (p. 9).

Insecurity management, in the context of Nigeria, therefore, has to do with addressing the root causes of insecurity, like poverty and unemployment through the initiating and implementing comprehensive strategies to protect citizens and resources from threats like crime, violence, and terrorism of which the broadcast media has a critical role to play in achieving peace in the society (Santas & Usman, 2013). Human security management focuses on protecting individuals and communities from various threats, encompassing not only traditional security concerns but also poverty, disease, and environmental degradation, aiming for a life free from fear and want (Iferenta & Akujuru, 2023; Magaji, Kari, Otakey & Jafaru, 2024; Olojede, 2022).

Effective security management has to do with utilising a multi-faceted approach, encompassing proactive measures, community engagement and addressing root causes of insecurity, such as poverty, inequality and lack of opportunities, among others (Olojede, 2022). Akingbohungebe (2024) affirms that insecurity management in Nigeria has to do with a holistic and multifaceted approach that encompasses effective governance, community engagement, strategic coordination among security agencies, and long-term investments in education and socio-economic development.

Nature of Security and the Need for Security Awareness in Nigeria

Nigeria possesses significant potential for development, given its large population, vast natural resources, expanding economy, and intellectual capacity. Despite these strengths, the country continues to struggle with widespread insecurity, which hinders its growth and stability (Nasiru, 2020). The security situation in Nigeria is complex, characterised by various threats, including terrorism, crime, and civil unrest. The country faces high levels of violent crime, including armed robbery, kidnapping, and other acts of violence. Cybersecurity threats, including cryptocurrency scams and AI-driven attacks, are also on the rise. Terrorism, particularly from groups like *Boko Haram* and *Islamic State West Africa Province*, poses a significant threat and have created an atmosphere of fear and uncertainty especially in areas with transport hubs, religious gatherings, and humanitarian facilities (Ugwu, Ekwueme & Nzekwe, n.d.; The Agora Policy Report, 2022).

The Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED), as cited in The Agora Policy Report (2022), documented 1,480 attacks attributed to *Boko Haram/Islamic*

State West Africa Province between July 2009 and August 2022. These attacks resulted in approximately 15,111 deaths and the displacement of over 3.2 million Nigerians. At their peak, these terrorist groups controlled 26 local government areas across Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States. Over time, their influence extended into other regions, including Kogi, Nasarawa, Kaduna, Kano, Plateau, Niger, Sokoto, and even the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), where they targeted government buildings, religious centres, transportation hubs, and public spaces (The Agora Policy Report, 2022). Obun-Andy, Aluko, & Abdulquadir (2021) described the ongoing security crisis as a persistent challenge to national peace and development, affecting nearly every part of the country. They noted that widespread incidents such as insurgency, banditry, herder-farmer clashes, and kidnappings continue to pose a major threat to Nigeria's economic stability and governance.

Broadcast Media and Audience Exposure to Programmes on Insecurity in Nigeria

Nigeria is currently grappling with numerous security threats, including terrorism, kidnapping, armed robbery and sexual violence, among others. The media has taken a leading role in addressing these challenges, with the Nigerian broadcast media playing a crucial role in security awareness campaigns. In fulfilment of its social responsibility, the broadcast media have developed numerous security-focused programmes designed to raise public consciousness and encourage citizen participation in combating insecurity. For instance, the Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria (FRCN), with its motto "*Uplifting the People and Uniting the Nation*," has introduced a security-focused programme titled "*Watch 360*", which airs every Sunday at 5:30 PM on its network service. This programme aims to instil security awareness among Nigerians, urging them to be more vigilant (Eruchi & Okolo, 2024; Gever & Nwabuzor, 2018).

Also, Ray Power FM, through a variety of call-in programmes is able to promote peacebuilding by using live phone calls and SMS messages to engage listeners in discussions on security and conflict resolution. Notable figures are often invited to these shows to provide expert insights, while listeners contribute by sharing their opinions or asking questions (Eruchi & Okolo, 2024; Olumide & Shuaib, 2020).

Similarly, Wazobia FM has developed programmes tailored to educate and empower communities, helping them understand their security environment and contribute to social change (Olumide & Shuaib, 2020). According to Mbachu, as cited in Okunna & Omenugha (2012), effective radio programming involves careful selection and arrangement of elements such as music, discussions, news, and other content to engage audiences. Momanyi (2015) argues that peacebuilding efforts must integrate civil society groups, religious leaders, government agencies, and the media to foster long-term harmony. By giving communities a voice in peace processes, the media can contribute to lasting solutions to insecurity.

Radio, in particular, has the potential to enhance peaceful coexistence by encouraging community-driven dialogue and solutions (Eruchi & Okolo, 2024). Some notable security programmes on different broadcast stations include: "*Crime Watch*"

(Channels Television), “*Crime Fighters*” (African Magic Family & NTA, supported by the Nigerian Police Force), “*The Eagle*” (Economic and Financial Crimes Commission - EFCC), “*Watch 360*”, “*Police Diary*” (Radio Nigeria), “*If You See Something, Say Something*” and “*Know Your Neighbor Now*” (aired on NTA), *Whistleblower Policy* (Federal Government’s anti-corruption initiative), “*Security is Everybody’s Business*” (Radio Nigeria, Enugu; Solid FM; Dream FM; and Sunrise 96.1 FM), “*Security Point of View*” (aired in Enugu State) (Abdullahi & Dango, 2023; Odishika, 2021; Ugwu, Ekwueme, & Nzekwe, n.d).

Role of Broadcast Media in Preventing Insecurity in Nigeria

The media play an indispensable role in ensuring national security by informing the public, raising awareness, and fostering vigilance. In Nigeria, where threats such as terrorism, kidnapping, and ethnic conflicts persist, the media serve as a critical tool for disseminating information on security threats and responses. During the *Boko Haram* insurgency, for instance, Nigerian media outlets actively informed the public about the group’s activities, government countermeasures, and safety protocols. Broadcast channels such as Channels TV and Premium Times provided regular updates and analytical reports that kept citizens informed and alert (Agbo, 2024). Ngige, Badekale & HammanJoda (2016, p. 58) highlight the media’s role in combating insecurity, stating: “The media is considered the fourth estate of the realm, a vital institution in the fight against terrorism worldwide. It serves as an intermediary, delivering essential security-related information from the government to the general public.” This underscores the media’s responsibility in ensuring security. However, its role can be manipulated either positively or negatively (Ngige, Badekale & HammanJoda, 2016, p. 58). They further note:

The media have been criticised for worsening insecurity and fueling conflicts in Nigeria due to their reporting patterns, which often prioritise commercial gains over national stability. Insurgents frequently exploit the media to amplify their propaganda, drawing greater attention to their activities.

This suggests that while the media can contribute to security enhancement, irresponsible journalism may escalate conflicts. In fulfilling their watchdog role, the media have taken the lead in providing timely information about security threats and the government’s response to them." The media, particularly the broadcast media, have played significant roles in peace-building by fostering dialogue and civic engagement. Community interaction programmes have provided a platform for residents to voice concerns, share security-related information, and propose solutions to conflicts (Eruchi & Okolo, 2024). Media interventions have proven that while they can incite conflicts, they also possess the power to mend fractured societies. Howard (cited in Akpan, 2018) describes the media’s “double-edged sword” effect, highlighting its capacity to both incite and resolve conflicts. Through structured programmes, the media facilitate open

discussions on conflicts, enabling communities to express grievances and collectively seek resolutions (Eruchi & Okolo, 2024).

The media's role in sharing information fosters national security. According to Momanyi (2015), radio serves as a crucial tool for conflict resolution, particularly in areas prone to violence, by providing factual information and facilitating peace-building efforts. Furthermore, during emergencies, the media help reduce panic by offering clear, accurate, and timely information, thereby guiding public behaviour and assisting security agencies in their response efforts (Agbo, 2024).

As stated, regular reporting on security incidents involving banditry, terrorism, and ritual killings raises public awareness and pressures the government into action. Providing airtime for in-depth discussions on issues such as terrorism, kidnapping, and armed robbery ensures that the public remains informed and engaged (Abdullahi & Dango, 2023). As the “fourth estate of the realm”, the broadcast media serve as society’s watchdogs, tasked with informing, educating, entertaining, and mobilising the public. Their influence extends across political, religious, economic, and social spheres, making them instrumental in governance, religious propagation, economic growth, and social development (Ezeakolam & Omowale, 2017). Because security remains one of Nigeria’s most pressing challenges, it has become one of the most covered topics in the media (Ide, Ojiakor-Umenze & Emeka, 2024, p. 24). Furthermore, the media serve as interventionist tools in peace negotiations, fostering communication between conflicting parties and promoting reconciliation. Effective conflict reporting prioritises objectivity, dialogue, and consensus-building to prevent further violence and instability (Saudat & Ogaga, 2017).

Impact of Broadcast Media Programmes on Security Awareness and Management in Nigeria

A dynamic media landscape ensures the free flow of information, facilitates dialogue, encourages civic engagement, and enhances accountability (Udeze & Onah, 2019). Over the years, conflicts of various intensities have occurred worldwide, significantly impacting human lives through loss, displacement, and the disruption of socio-economic activities. The scale of these violent conflicts, once unimaginable, now poses serious challenges to global peace and development (Udeze & Onah, 2019). Separatist movements in different regions often fuel conflicts, drawing in government forces, militant groups, and civil society actors (Nnamani & Maduewesi, 2016).

As emphasised by Briggs (cited in Okoro *et al* 2017), the media play a significant role in shaping conflict narratives. Saudat & Ogaga (2017, p. 174) affirm that: *"The media serve as a critical agent in the construction of knowledge, influencing public perception and framing societal issues."* Mass media shape reality through the information they disseminate, affecting public discourse and actions that either escalate or de-escalate conflicts. Their influence led the Nigerian government to regulate the content of conflict-related information to control narratives and maintain stability (Saudat & Ogaga (2017). Ide, Ojiakor-Umenze & Emeka (2024, p. 24) further state:

As a key element of mass communication, the media significantly shape public opinion and influence how security challenges are perceived in society. Radio broadcasts, in particular, provide crucial updates on security issues, equipping citizens with essential information.

This underscores the media's ability to shape public attitudes toward security concerns. Nwabueze & Ebeze (2013) highlight that the media not only enhance awareness but also influence behaviours, societal attitudes, and decision-making processes. It is a tool that fosters public discourse, circulates ideas, and molds collective values (Kamal, Jamilu, Mukhtar & Ahmed, 2024). According to the Nigeria Broadcasting Code (2016, 6th Edition):

Broadcasting must positively influence society, setting the agenda for socio-economic, cultural and political development. Through mass media, Nigerians should engage in discourse that enriches public life and fosters national progress, in alignment with the guiding principles of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) (p. 8).

The surveillance function of mass media play a critical role in enforcing social order, discouraging crime, and exposing societal vices (McQuail, 2000). Laswell (cited in Giddens, 2006) argues that media exposure is vital in crime prevention, as increased publicity often deters offenders. Broadcast media also have a social responsibility to provide timely information, promote national unity, and challenge negative perceptions about Nigeria while operating within the country's legal framework (Iheanacho, Jumbo & Etumnu, 2021; Onyemaobi & Okpoko, 2023). Many media programmes in Nigeria focus on raising crime awareness and deterring criminal activities. Examples include "Police Diary" on Radio Nigeria and "Dan Sanda Abokin Kowa," which airs on multiple stations. Additionally, crime-specific newspaper columns, television documentaries and radio discussions further reinforce crime prevention efforts. Security-focused public service announcements (PSAs) and jingles are also regularly aired on various Nigerian television and radio stations (Nwabueze & Ebeze, 2013).

Nwabueze (2009) observes that individuals who consume high levels of crime-related media content often perceive crime rates as higher than reported statistics suggest, leading them to adopt more precautionary measures. This demonstrates how media narratives influence public perceptions of safety and security. Beyond crime reporting, media influence extends to shaping social behaviour, raising awareness on societal challenges such as child abuse, domestic violence, human trafficking, and terrorism (Olumide & Shuaib, 2020). By designing television and radio programmes focused on crime deterrence and community engagement, the media actively encourage proactive security measures. Given its extensive reach, the media can mobilise public awareness on security matters more effectively than any other institution (Gever & Nwabuzor, 2018; Kamal, Jamilu, Mukhtar & Ahmed, 2024).

The media's ability to either de-escalate or fuel conflict depends on its content and framing. Responsible journalism plays a constructive role in conflict resolution by promoting peace and stability (Jackson, 2012). When media outlets prioritise objectivity and factual reporting, they foster peace-building efforts and encourage non-violent conflict resolution strategies. Conversely, sensationalist or biased reporting can exacerbate tensions and provoke unrest (Nnamani & Maduewesi, 2016). Media influence security management positively and negatively. Kiche & Simiyu (2022) and Mugambi (2020) identify several ways in which broadcast media influence security management: Providing accurate information, disseminating public alerts, reducing conflict escalation, facilitating leadership communication, escalating conflict, spreading propaganda, cultural influence, exposing state secrets.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the social responsibility media theory, supported by agenda-setting theory.

Social Responsibility Media Theory

The social responsibility media theory originated from the 1947 Hutchins Commission on the Freedom of the Press in the United States. It emerged as a response to libertarian theory, which advocated for unrestricted press freedom. Social responsibility theory seeks to balance media freedom with accountability, ensuring that the press operates ethically and serves the public interest (Anaeto, Onabajo & Osifeso, 2008). The theory posits that media organisations have an obligation to serve society responsibly by adhering to professional standards of truth, accuracy, balance and objectivity. Specifically, the social responsibility theory mandates that:

- a. The media should fulfil obligations to society, including promoting security and safeguarding lives and property.
- b. Truthfulness, accuracy, and objectivity should guide media reportage.
- c. Media organisations should regulate themselves within legal and institutional frameworks.
- d. Content that incites violence, crime, or civil unrest should be avoided.
- e. The media should reflect societal diversity, granting access to various viewpoints and ensuring the right of reply.
- f. Society has the right to expect high-performance standards from the media and government intervention is only justified for the public good.
- g. Media professionals should be accountable to society, employers, and market forces (McQuail, 1987 in Anaeto, Onabajo & Osifeso, 2008).

Maruf (2023) outlines several strengths of Social Responsibility Theory which include aligning media operations with public opinion and democratic principles, ensuring factual reporting through regulatory oversight, curbing unethical journalism practices, such as sensationalism and misinformation, promoting diversity and pluralism

in news content and amplifying the voices of marginalised groups, fostering inclusivity. However, some weaknesses exist as ethical standards are often subjective and difficult to define, no universal regulatory framework exists to ensure consistency, overregulation which may infringe on press freedom, limiting investigative journalism.

Despite these limitations, social responsibility theory is highly relevant to this study, as it underscores the role of the media in promoting national security, peace, and public awareness. Security is a prerequisite for national development, and the media is expected to function as a watchdog, warning citizens and security agencies of potential threats (Ezeakolam & Omowale, 2017). Thus, if the Nigerian broadcast media effectively discharge their surveillance role, they can prevent security threats, promote peace and contribute to national stability.

Agenda-Setting Theory

The agenda-setting theory traces its roots to Walter Lippmann's 1922 book *Public Opinion*. Lippmann (2020) argues that the media shape public perceptions by presenting selected images of reality. The theory gained prominence when Cohen (1963) famously stated that “the press may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but it is stunningly successful in telling its readers what to think about.” However, McCombs & Shaw (1972) were the first scholars to formalise the theory in their groundbreaking study on media influence in the 1968 U.S. presidential election.

This theory asserts that the media play a crucial role in determining which issues the public perceives as important by repeatedly emphasising specific topics. Insecurity, for instance, becomes a national concern not necessarily because it is the most pressing issue, but because the media continually highlight it (Ide, Ojiakor-Umenze & Emeka, 2024). Agenda-setting has been central to research in political science and communication studies, particularly in understanding how media influence public opinion on topics like crime, terrorism, and national security (McCombs, 2004). The theory emphasises that media influence is determined by selection of newsworthy stories – what topics the media choose to report and prominence and frequency of reporting – how often and where stories appear (e.g., headlines, front pages, prime-time news) as well as framing of issues – The angle from which a story is told (Baran & Davis, 2003).

According to McCombs & Shaw (1972), the process of agenda-setting involves a transfer of issue salience from the media to the public. Over time, the public perceives issues that the media emphasise as more critical. This aligns with the findings of Abdullahi & Dango (2023), who suggest that the media play a pivotal role in shaping national discourse on security matters. Kamal, Jamilu, Mukhtar & Ahmed (2024) further expand on this, stating that: "The agenda-setting theory, in relation to crime, highlights the media's key role in shaping public opinion and selectively disseminating information. The prominence given to certain crime stories through frequent reporting, headline display, or positioning influences discussions on societal issues" (p. 281). Miller (2001) identifies three main agendas within the theory:

- a. Media Agenda – The set of issues that media outlets emphasise.
- b. Public Agenda – The issues that the public perceives as important.
- c. Policy Agenda – The priorities of policymakers, legislators, and government officials.

The connection between these agendas determines how media narratives influence both public perception and policymaking. The strengths of agenda-setting theory explain how media influence public discourse by reporting security issues (Baran & Davis, 2003). The limitations of Agenda-Setting Theory are the assumption that media consumers are passive, whereas many individuals actively engage with and challenge media narratives (Kamal et al., 2024). The Theory fails to account for audience selectivity – people often choose media that align with their existing beliefs, limiting the impact of agenda-setting and it does not explain why some issues fail to gain traction despite extensive media coverage (Severin & Tankard, 2001). Furthermore, it overlooks competing media sources – in today’s digital age, audiences receive news from multiple platforms, diluting the agenda-setting power of traditional media (Reese, 2007).

Despite its limitations, agenda-setting theory remains relevant to this study as it underscores the media’s capacity to shape national discourse on insecurity. By repeatedly highlighting security concerns, the media can influence public perception, pressure policymakers, and drive national security strategies (Gever & Nwabuzor, 2015; Kamal *et al* 2024).

Methodology

This study adopted library research design in sourcing data for this study - collecting data through studying and comprehending information from textbooks, journals, articles, virtual resources and documents. The secondary method enabled us rely on pre-existing data to take a position on the subject of the study. As a novel theme, this procedure became the most “viable means of collecting relevant and contemporary data with which to shed light on the study” (Modinat & Aliede, 2023, p. 3). Synthesis discourse analysis was used for the analysis of the data collected in the study.

Discussion

Nigeria is currently under a period of multifaceted security challenges characterised by various threats, including terrorism, insurgency, drug trafficking, cultism, militancy, crime, and civil unrest and many other acts of violent crimes. Cybersecurity threats, including cryptocurrency scams and AI-driven attacks, are also on the rise. This is evident as scholars like Obun-Andy, Aluko & Abdulquadir (2021), Ottah & Okpoko (2024), The Agora Policy Report (2022), Ugwu, Ekwueme, & Nzekwe (n.d), etc. who acknowledged the fact that the nature of insecurity in Nigeria is multifaceted. While Ottah & Okpoko (2024), advocate for a robust communication policy, and investigative journalism against security challenges.

The audience is exposed to broadcast media programmes on insecurity which are broadcast to them using multifaceted programmes genres, including: news, discussion, interviews, phone-in, commentary, and direct reporting among others even though cases of under-reportage and inappropriate reportage exist among some broadcast media outfits. This is evident as scholars such as Achakpaikyo *et al* (2022), Aondover *et al* (2025), Don *et al* (2024), Ehigiator, Asemah & Nwaoboli (2023), Elliot, Ifeoma & Etumnu (2024), Musa, Che, Isma & Siti (2024), Onah (2020), Saudat & Ogaga (2017), Soho (2024), Tarlumun, Ujia & Agada (2024) acknowledged the role of broadcast media in security management and the audience exposure to the security programmes broadcast to them. Ehigiator, Asemah & Nwaoboli (2023), however, state that while there was a high level of coverage of insecurity by the media, the issue did not receive sufficient prominence compared to other topics like politics.

The broadcast media have tremendous impact on insecurity management by raising public awareness, disseminating critical information, fostering a culture of vigilance, holding security agencies accountable, and countering extremist narratives among others. However, the broadcast media sometime engage framing security issues in the way that promote regional and ethnic sentiments rather than addressing the real drivers of the insecurity. This is evident in studies conducted by different scholars which point to different impact of broadcast media programmes in the management of insecurity (Abdullahi & Dango, 2023; Achakpaikyo *et al* 2022; Agbo, 2024; Bappayo, 2023; Biwot & Mberia, 2019; Eruchi & Okolo, 2024; Gever & Nwabuzor, 2018; Ibrahim, 2021; Kiche & Simiyu, 2022; Ngige, Badekale & HammanJoda, 2016; Nwankwo *et al*, 2023; Ogu, 2024; Ojo & Ayobolu, 2020; Okey-Oguej, 2016; Oluwaseun, 2024; Onyemaobi & Okpoko, 2023; Orlu-Orlu, 2017; Sanni, 2022).

Furthermore, the broadcast media face a number of challenges in the management of insecurity and some of the challenges include: limited access, ownership influence, political inference, ethno-religious sentiments, illiteracy, poor signals, poor power supply, lack of professionalism, poor training, poor funding, lack of security for media professionals, intimidation, outdated equipment, misinformation and fake news. This is evident as scholars have affirmed that the broadcast media are faced with different challenges that if not addressed, can hinder them from achieving the desired success in the management of security (Achakpaikyo *et al*, 2022; Agbo, 2024; Gonina, Ngantem & Dapiya, 2020; Ibrahim, 2021; Nwokoro, Akpan & Peter, 2023; Ojo & Ayobolu, 2020; Tarlumun, Ujia & Agada, 2024; Udo, 2022).

Conclusion

Nigeria is currently under a period of multifaceted security challenges characterised by various threats, including terrorism, insurgency, drug trafficking, cultism, militancy, crime, and civil unrest. There are also high levels of violent crime, including armed robbery, kidnapping, and other acts of violence. Cybersecurity threats, including cryptocurrency scams and AI-driven attacks, are also on the rise. It can be acknowledged

that the audience is exposed to broadcast media programmes on insecurity which are broadcast to them using multifaceted programme genres, including: news, discussion, interviews, phone-in, commentary, and direct reporting among others even though cases of under-reportage and inappropriate reportage exist among some broadcast media outfits.

Subsequently, the broadcast media have tremendous impact on insecurity management by raising public awareness, disseminating critical information, fostering a culture of vigilance, holding security agencies accountable, and countering extremist narratives among others. However, the broadcast media sometime engage framing security issues in the way that promote regional and ethnic sentiments rather than addressing the real drivers of the insecurity. The broadcast media face a number of challenges in the management of insecurity and some of the challenges include: limited access, ownership influence, political inference, ethno-religious sentiments, illiteracy, poor signals, poor power supply, lack of professionalism, poor training, poor funding, lack of security for media professionals, intimidation, outdated equipment, misinformation and fake news. However, the broadcast media have positive contribution to make in the management of insecurity when used effectively. Thus, prioritise balanced and informed reporting on security issues, avoiding sensationalism and promoting national unity over regional or ethnic sentiments.

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